

Microsecond-Lived Luminescence in Semiconductor Quantum Dots and Metal Nanoclusters: Unveiling a Common Origin

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ABSTRACT Nanoscale materials, including semiconductor quantum dots (QDs) and metal nanoclusters (NCs), exhibit extraordinary photoluminescence (PL) properties compared to their bulk counterparts. However, their study has largely been separate, lacking direct comparison. This study provides compelling evidence of a shared photophysical mechanism underlying the μ s-lived luminescence in both colloidal organically-capped PbS QDs and gold (Au) NCs, despite their differing material compositions and electronic structures. The absorption spectra underscore fundamental differences: PbS QDs, with a mean size of approximately 3 nm, exhibit sharp excitonic peaks due to quantum confinement (QC), while Au NCs, approximately 1.4 nm in size, show broad, featureless absorption indicative of molecular-like states. However, both PbS QDs and Au NCs display similar long-lived μ s-range PL lifetimes and large Stokes shifts. Crucially, the study reveals that when the PL and lifetime spectra of both materials are normalized and spectrally aligned, their lifetime spectra overlap remarkably, while their PL spectra match closely

in their peaks, suggesting a shared underlying mechanism governing their emission properties. This finding challenges the conventional view that QC solely dictates the PL of semiconductor QDs with μ s-lived PL. Instead, metal-sulfur interactions are suggested to play a pivotal role in governing the long-lived emission in both materials.

KEYWORDS: quantum dots, metal nanoclusters, photoluminescence; averaged lifetime; lifetime distribution

Materials can be classified into three primary categories based on their electrical conductivity and electronic structure: insulators, semiconductors, and conductors (metals). These classifications arise from the nature of the electron energy bands in solids—specifically the valence and conduction bands—and the availability of charge carriers for conduction. Insulators are materials with a relatively large energy bandgap (typically greater than 4 eV) between the valence band and the conduction band. Though insulators, when doped with appropriate activators (such as rare-earth or transition metal ions), can serve as highly efficient luminophores, we leave them beyond the scope of this study.

Semiconductors and metals exhibit a moderate bandgap or the absence of a bandgap, respectively, which clearly reflects in the availability of charge carriers. Bulk metals have a high density of free electrons in the conduction band due to the overlap of the valence and conduction bands. Therefore, noble metals like gold (Au), silver (Ag), and copper (Cu) are widely known for their surface plasmon resonances (SPRs),^{1,2} which involve the collective oscillation of conduction electrons at the metal-dielectric interface. These surface plasmons enable metals to strongly interact with light, but this phenomenon does not lead to efficient photoluminescence (PL) in the bulk form. Indeed, the free electron gas causes the energy absorbed from light or

other excitation sources to be quickly dissipated as heat through non-radiative processes, primarily via electron-electron and electron-phonon interactions. Hence, bulk metals cannot efficiently convert absorbed energy into light. For example, the PL quantum yield (QY) of bulk gold film is on the order of only $10^{-8}\%$.³

Bulk semiconductor crystals exhibit a bandgap – for example, a galena (natural mineral of PbS) crystal possesses⁴ a narrow bandgap of around 0.41 eV at room temperature – that allows electrons excited to the conduction band to fall back into the valence band, emitting photons in the process (radiative recombination). However, they can be less efficient luminescent materials, comparing to their nanocrystalline counterparts.^{5,6} This inefficiency can be attributed to several fundamental reasons, including high rates of phonon emission, low exciton binding energy, Auger recombination, and defect-related traps. These factors result in PL quenching, which occurs predominantly in the material volume.⁷ In contrast, surface defects are believed to mainly quench PL in nanomaterials.⁸

Nanosized materials of both semiconductors and metals, bridging the gap between atomic and bulk scales, may offer a wealth of tunable and enhanced optical phenomena. In the case of semiconductors, when the spatial dimensions of the crystal become comparable to or smaller than the exciton Bohr radius, the nanomaterial exhibits quantum confinement (QC) effects, causing discrete, size-dependent electronic and optical properties⁵. Lead sulfide (PbS) has a large exciton Bohr radius (18 nm), where the excited electron and hole contribute equally due to their similarly small effective masses.^{9,10} This is because PbS has a highly symmetric crystal structure¹⁰, and the effective mass associated with a band is inversely proportional to the curvature of the corresponding energy band near its extremum¹¹. This offers an extreme QC regime for PbS nanoparticles (NPs), which are often called quantum dots (QDs) with sizes

typically a few nanometers (usually 2–10 nm). In this size regime, the QD diameter is still much larger than the crystalline lattice constant (0.594 nm for the rock salt structure of bulk PbS),¹⁰ which validates the assumption of the periodicity (translational symmetry) of the semiconductor crystal. A typical number of atoms in such QDs varies from hundreds to thousands.

PbS QDs smaller than ~3 nm have been shown to be octahedrons with eight (111) facets, where these facets are completely terminated by Pb atoms.^{12,13,14} Above this size, PbS QDs are truncated octahedrons up to ~4.7 nm. The shape of larger PbS QDs transitions to cuboctahedrons with eight (111) hexagonal facets and six (100) square facets.^{12,13} Again, the (111) facets are terminated with Pb atoms and the (100) facets are stoichiometric. Notably, organic ligand molecules such as oleic acid (OA) have been shown to bind only to the lead atoms, leaving sulfur atoms at the surface unpassivated.¹⁵ The optical properties, such as absorption and PL, can be tuned by variation in QD sizes, typically from the short-wavelength infrared (SWIR) to the near-infrared (NIR) regions.^{16,17} These variations in optical absorption transitions can be well described by various theoretical models such as, e.g., four-band envelope-function calculations.¹⁸ The PL QY of PbS QDs is exceptionally high for the addressed technologically important spectral region, reaching up to 60–80%.^{19,20,21,22}

Colloidal metal NPs with diameters of 5–100 nm are popular for their localized SPR (LSPR).^{2,23} For instance, Au NPs exhibit an absorption peak between ~520–570 nm, depending on their sizes.²⁴ However, the PL QY of these Au NPs is still very low (< 1%).^{25,26}

Upon further decrease in size of Au NPs (~2.3 nm–1.7 nm) a transition from metallic (plasmonic) to non-metallic (luminescent) character takes place.²⁷ This transition occurs^{27,28} between Au₃₃₃ and Au₁₄₄ and is accompanied with transformation of face-centered cubic (fcc) cores (similar to bulk gold) to non-fcc cores. Ultrasmall (<1.7 nm) non-metallic gold

nanoparticles are called nanoclusters (NCs) and are characterized by the emergence of discrete electronic states and molecular-like HOMO-LUMO gap. These small gold NCs behave more like molecules lacking the continuous size-tunable properties (true QC effect) seen in semiconductor QDs. Since collective electronic excitations are no longer possible the LSPR disappears which gives rise to single-electron transitions in Au NCs resulting in dramatic increase of PL efficiency. For instance, 1.7 nm orange-emitting Au NCs with PL peak at 565 nm (similar to bulk gold)^{3,26} reveal²⁹ PL QY around 4% which is 8 orders of magnitude more effective than bulk gold. Benefiting from³⁰ excellent photostability after proper passivation (e.g. via thiolated ligands), large Stokes shift, extremely high surface-to-volume ratio, low toxicity and biocompatibility, Au NCs become highly competitive with semiconductor QDs^{31,32} for applications in the biomedical diagnosis such as cell labelling, biosensing or phototherapy.

Notably, small semiconductor PbS NCs (few to tens of atoms) have also been studied, where the term nanocluster highlights a transition to molecular-like behavior. Despite the discrete energy levels, nanocrystals or QDs retain their bulk-like band structure (for sizes down to about 2 nm), meaning that the material still has conduction and valence bands, but the size of the crystal restricts the electron and hole movement - kinetic energies of carriers are quantized (QC effect). At the size scale of nanoclusters, which are smaller than QDs, the electronic states are best described by molecular orbital theory, similar to how the electronic states in a molecule are determined by the bonding and interactions between individual atoms. The HOMO-LUMO gap replaces the concept of a bandgap, and the energy levels arise from the interactions of a small, fixed number of atoms, not from the broad bands of a crystal lattice.

PbS NCs as large as about 1.5 nm (<90 atoms) absorb^{11,33} near 2 eV, which is about five times the energy gap of bulk PbS. Further size reduction to 1 nm (30+ atoms) results in an additional

blueshift of optical transitions¹¹ to about 2.5 eV. PbS NCs consisting of a few atoms exhibit HOMO-LUMO transitions³⁴ near 4 eV, which is ten times larger than the bulk bandgap. Unlike in QDs governed by the QC effect, on the molecular-like level there is no longer a direct correspondence between the reduction in the number of atoms and the blueshift in optical transitions.^{34,35}

It is important to note that, compared to QDs, PbS NCs are more challenging to synthesize, study, and stabilize due to their susceptibility to oxidation, aggregation, and dissolution. As a result, small PbS NCs are primarily of interest in fundamental research, while the primary research focus remains on PbS QDs.

Despite the different nature of these materials, nanoscale PbS and metallic NCs reveal a number of similarities, including relatively long μs -range PL lifetimes^{19,36,37,38} and large Stokes shifts.^{20,38,39}

However, even after several decades of investigation, there is no consensus on the origin of this long-lived PL. The lack of a comprehensive understanding in this area has led to the publication of numerous reviews, which, while providing partial insights, do not fully address the underlying problem. Moreover, PL studies of nanoscale semiconductors and metals are, *a priori*, treated as separate disciplines, and direct inter-system comparisons are either absent or extremely limited.

This study is the first to report similarities in the long-lived PL of semiconductor PbS QDs and metal Au NCs, suggesting a shared mechanism underlying their PL. Through an extensive discussion, we propose a possible origin of PL in these materials.

Results and discussion

Absorption and PL spectra

The comparative analysis of the normalized PL and absorption spectra for PbS QDs (relative concentration 6.25%) and Au NCs is presented in Figure 1. The absorption spectrum of the PbS QDs features a prominent excitonic peak at approximately 1.42 eV, characteristics of well-defined QC effects in these semiconductor nanostructures. In contrast, the absorption spectrum of the Au NCs lacks a distinct excitonic peak, with absorption arising from a combination of intraband and weak interband transitions.⁴⁰ This results in a broad, continuous spectrum devoid of fine structure.⁴⁰

Figure 1. Normalized absorption (dash-dotted lines) and PL (solid lines) spectra of PbS QDs (blue lines) with a relative concentration of 6.25% and Au NCs (red lines). The absorption spectra of Au NCs, redshifted by 0.33 eV and 0.38 eV, are represented by purple and green dotted lines, respectively.

When the absorption spectrum of the Au NCs is redshifted by 0.33 eV, a direct comparison of Au and PbS absorptions, normalized at their high-energy tails, becomes possible. This comparison underscores the fundamentally different mechanisms underlying light absorption in these two materials.

The spectral position of the PL band, PL broadening, and Stokes shift of PbS QDs have been shown to depend on factors such as the passivating ligand, nanocrystal size, and concentration.^{19,41,42} The homogeneous linewidth broadening of PbS QDs has been reported to be approximately 0.1 eV,^{20,43} contributing significantly to the ensemble PL broadening, which is around 0.2 eV (Figure 1).

The PL spectrum of Au NCs (Figure 1) is particularly broad, spanning the visible (VIS) and near-infrared (NIR) regions (550–1200 nm), with a maximum near 740 nm (1.64 eV), situated at the edge of the red spectral region. This is consistent with previously synthesized Au NCs.^{44,45} Unlike some reports where the PL of Au NCs is described as consisting of two distinct bands^{46,47,48} the PL observed here appears as a single band with a slightly asymmetrical near-Gaussian shape extending toward longer wavelengths, a characteristics typical of Au NCs PL. Previous studies have shown that the PL peak position of water-soluble Au NCs can be tuned (to some extent) by selecting appropriate ligands.³⁰ Generally, Au NCs of similar sizes exhibit PL peaks in the range of ~640–750 nm⁴⁹ and do not extend significantly into the NIR beyond 850 nm.^{30,50,51} In contrast, the PL of TA-capped or TA+PEG-capped Au NCs in water is broader,^{44,52} with peaks located at ~740–820 nm under UV excitation. Additionally, it has been demonstrated⁵³ that, unlike in Au NPs where electron-phonon interactions dominate, electron-electron scattering governs hot electron relaxation in Au NCs, resulting in their broad ensemble PL.

To facilitate a direct comparison, the absorption and PL spectra of the Au NCs were energetically redshifted by 0.38 eV, aligning their PL emission peak with that of the PbS QDs (Figure 1). The Stokes shift of the Au NCs, defined as the energy difference between the absorption onset and the PL peak, is significantly larger than that of the PbS QDs. Additionally, the PL spectrum of the Au NCs is much broader, spanning an energy range of 1–2.3 eV. This broadness indicates a distribution of emissive states, potentially stemming from size dispersion and the inherent electronic structure heterogeneity of the clusters. In contrast, the PbS QDs exhibit a narrower PL profile, reflecting their more uniform electronic properties.

At first glance, it may seem that, similar to absorption, the emission mechanisms in these materials are fundamentally different. However, in the following section, we provide compelling evidence highlighting the similarities in the emission processes of PbS QDs and Au NCs.

Lifetime spectral dispersions

Similar to PbS QDs, the red/NIR emission of Au NCs with thiolated ligands has been reported to be relatively slow, typically occurring in the μs range.⁵⁴ Figure 2 presents a detailed comparison of the intensity-averaged lifetime spectral dispersions alongside the corresponding PL spectra for PbS QDs (relative concentration 25%) and Au NCs. The intensity-averaged lifetimes were calculated from their PL decay profiles using equation 1.

Figure 2. Normalized PL spectra (solid lines) and intensity-averaged lifetimes (symbols) calculated using a fitting-free model (eq (1)) from experimental PL profiles of PbS QDs (purple) with a relative concentration of 25% and Au NCs (dark cyan) as a function of emission wavelength. The PL and lifetime spectra of PbS QDs, blueshifted by 0.45 eV to achieve optimal overlap with the lifetime spectrum of Au NCs (dark cyan circles), are shown in green. A normalization scaling factor of 1.08 was applied to the shifted lifetimes of PbS QDs, represented by green open diamonds.

The lifetime dispersion curves for both samples exhibit a characteristic uniformity, with a spectral lifetime maximum evident in each case. For Au NCs, this lifetime maximum is closely aligned with the PL peak. In contrast, for PbS QDs, there is a distinct shift of approximately 40 meV between the lifetime maximum and the PL spectrum peak.

The lifetime peak for PbS QDs has been observed⁵⁵ and discussed in detail elsewhere.⁵⁶ Briefly, the decrease in lifetime from the peak toward higher energies was attributed to a

reduction in radiative lifetime, as expected due to the QC effect. Conversely, variations in lifetime on the lower-energy shoulder of the lifetime maximum were suggested to arise from external factors, such as an increased likelihood of non-radiative relaxation in larger QDs. A similar phenomenon can also be observed in indirect semiconductor QDs, such as Si, as the emission energy or wavelength approaches the bandgap.⁵⁷

Surprisingly, there are very few reports presenting dispersions of lifetimes or rates for Au NCs. A similar lifetime spectral extremum near the PL peak was described by Link et al.,⁴⁸ who suggested the involvement of several degenerate or closely spaced energy levels. Additionally, several studies have reported a decrease in lifetime for Au NCs in the visible region as the emission shifts to shorter wavelengths.^{39,58,59} Previous investigations of thiolated Au NCs^{60,61,62} demonstrated no strict quantitative correlation between the size (number of gold atoms) and the spectral position of the PL emission peak for larger NCs (>13 atoms). Thus, the QC model cannot be applied to explain this phenomenon.

To account for the intrinsic differences between the electronic structures of PbS and Au materials and their respective emission energy ranges, a spectral blueshift of 0.45 eV was applied to the PbS QDs data. This adjustment yielded the best alignment of the lifetime curves, as depicted in Figure 2, with the light green and dark cyan curves representing the PbS and Au samples, respectively. Additionally, a small scaling factor of 1.08 was applied to account for differences in absolute lifetime values, which depend on various parameters, including the excitation wavelength and surrounding environment of the particles.

Despite structural differences – Au NCs comprising approximately 25 atoms⁴⁵ and PbS QDs containing over 500 atoms¹¹ – their normalized lifetime spectral dispersions show remarkable overlap. With the same energy adjustment, the normalized PL spectrum of PbS QDs aligns

closely with that of Au NCs near the PL maximum. This close correspondence between the two systems provides insight into the similar fundamental mechanisms governing their nanoscale photophysical processes, despite differences in composition, size, and atomic count. For comparison, we also examined other materials, including Si nanocrystals. The lifetime dispersions of these materials were fundamentally different from those presented in Figure 2, further underscoring the unique similarities observed between PbS QDs and Au NCs.

This surprising observation suggests that the PL of PbS QDs is not solely governed by the QC effect, contrary to what is postulated in numerous studies. This conclusion follows directly from the absence of the QC effect in thiolated Au NCs. Several indirect pieces of evidence supporting this interpretation have been provided in previous studies^{20,41,63} For instance, the μ s-range lifetime of PbS QDs is at least an order of magnitude longer than expected for a direct bandgap semiconductor, even when dielectric screening is taken into account.⁵⁶ Moreover, the spectral position of the PL peak in PbS QDs is a linear function of absorption energies, with a slope of 1 only for energies below approximately 1 eV.⁶³ At higher energies, this slope changes to about 0.5.^{20,63} Given the equality of the effective masses of charge carriers in PbS, this behavior is consistent with emission originating from a state where only one charge carrier is confined. Fernée et al.²⁰ suggested that unpassivated sulfur atoms on the surface of PbS QDs could act as shallow traps for holes. The PbS QD dispersions in this study exhibit absorption peaks well above 1 eV, which may indicate the presence of localized states^{20,41} that lead to the confinement of only one charge carrier.

Au NCs can exhibit both fluorescence (ns-range) and phosphorescence (μ s-range), depending on factors such as the number of gold atoms, NC structure, and functionalization. For instance, the size-dependent PL properties of dendrimer-encapsulated small Au NCs have been shown to

align well with the Jellium energy scaling law, where $E_{\text{Fermi}}/N^{1/3}$ represents the Fermi energy of bulk gold.⁶⁴ Larger NCs (>20 atoms) can be described using a modified free-electron model, which incorporates corrections for electronic screening effects and harmonic distortion in the potential energy well. These types of Au NCs typically exhibit fluorescence with lifetimes of the order of a few nanoseconds. Similarly, fully inorganic Au NCs with a size of approximately 1.1 nm, emitting at around 340 nm, have also demonstrated fluorescence with lifetimes in the ns range.⁶⁵

In contrast, Au NCs functionalized with thiol-based ligands exhibit significant diversity, with PL lifetimes spanning a broad range from ns to μs . For example, DHLA-capped single Au NCs ($\lambda_{em} \approx 640$ nm, $d \approx 1.5$ nm) exhibited a lifetime of 7 ns.⁶⁶ Similarly, 6-aza-2-thiothymine (ATT)-protected Au NCs ($\lambda_{em} \approx 528$ nm, $d \approx 2$ nm) showed a lifetime of 13 ns.⁶⁷ Interestingly, introducing L-arginine (Arg) into the capping layer extended the lifetime significantly to 86 ns.

Some thiolate-protected Au NCs have also been shown to emit with lifetimes in the range of ~100–187 ns across different spectral regions, depending on the number of gold atoms. For instance, Au₂₈₍₃₆₎ emitted at 760–770 nm, while Au₄₄₍₅₂₎ emitted at 950 nm.⁶⁸ The lifetime of GSH-capped Au NCs ($\lambda_{em} \approx 565$ nm, $d \approx 1.7$ nm) was found to depend on the excitation wavelength: under resonant 530 nm excitation, the lifetime was 25 ns, whereas at 420 nm excitation, it extended to 1.63 μs .²⁹

Lipoic acid-stabilized Au NCs, with or without PEG or zwitterion functional groups, and emitting near 720–750 nm, were reported to have lifetimes in the range of ~180–400 ns.^{44,69} Sub- μs range lifetimes have also been observed in protein-functionalized Au NCs. For instance, insulin-Au NCs exhibited PL lifetimes of ~40 ns.⁷⁰ BSA-capped Au NCs emitting in the 630–690 nm range demonstrated PL lifetimes of ~170–193 ns.^{71,72,73} Other studies on similar BSA-

capped Au NCs reported two PL lifetime components: one in the ns range and another around $\sim 1.5 \mu\text{s}$.^{49,47}

Even though some studies on Au NCs protected with thiolate ligands report lifetimes in the ns or sub- μs range, most often, Au NCs functionalized with these organic ligands and emitting in the red or NIR exhibit phosphorescence with μs -range lifetimes.^{74,75,76,77,78} Thiol-capped Au NCs can be described as $\text{Au}_n(\text{SR})_m$, where SR represents a thiolate ligand. These NCs typically feature a core-shell structure, consisting of a symmetrical metallic Au(0) core surrounded by an exterior shell composed of staple-like motifs ($\text{SR}-[\text{Au}(\text{I})-\text{SR}]_x$), often referred to as "semi-rings." For example, Au_{25} may comprise⁷⁹ an icosahedral Au_{13} core enveloped by six $-\text{S}-\text{Au}-\text{S}-\text{Au}-\text{S}$ staple motifs. Thiolated Au NCs have been shown^{29,78} to contain both Au(0) and Au(I) oxidation states, with a high proportion of Au(I) localized on the surface, which is believed to play an important role in their PL.⁸⁰

There is yet an ongoing debate within the scientific community regarding the role of Au(0) core and staple motifs in the phosphorescence of Au NCs. Aggregated organometallic compounds, such as Au(I)-SR complexes, have been shown to exhibit properties similar to those of Au NCs, including large Stokes shifts and long μs -range lifetimes.⁷⁸ Notably, the luminescence of aggregated organic molecules is typically fluorescent,^{81,82} highlighting the importance of the metallic components in the phosphorescence of organometallic compounds.

Interestingly, the effective PL of Au(I)-SR complexes is induced upon their aggregation, whereas such non-aggregated complexes often exhibit no PL in solution.⁷⁸ This phenomenon, known as aggregation-induced emission (AIE), is believed to arise from the restriction of intramolecular motion, such as rotational and vibronic modes. This restriction likely reduces non-radiative relaxation pathways for excited electrons, enhancing radiative recombination.

In this context, the staple motifs $\text{SR}[\text{Au(I)-SR}]_x$ in the protective framework of $\text{Au}_n(\text{SR})_m$ NCs can be viewed as an aggregation of Au(I)-SR complexes on the surface of a NC. This aggregation is mediated by covalent Au-S bonds with the metallic Au(0) core.⁷⁸ Recent compelling studies^{75,78} have suggested that AIE, with the crucial involvement of Au(I)-thiolates, may be a possible origin of the phosphorescence observed in Au NCs.

However, PbS QDs with OA ligands on their surface lack staple-like motifs, yet their PL closely resembles that of thiolated Au NCs (Figure 2). This observation makes the scenario of AIE as the primary mechanism responsible for phosphorescence in Au NCs seem improbable. Furthermore, we propose that the long-lived PL may originate not from the staple motifs but from the thiolate ligands themselves, specifically due to the presence of sulfur atoms bonded to metal atoms rather than the structural motifs. These metal-sulfur (M-S, where M is a metal atom) bonds may serve as a common characteristic between Au NCs and PbS QDs, with gold (Au) and lead (Pb) having closely related atomic numbers of 79 and 82, respectively.

Recently, phosphine-halide-protected $\text{Au}_{11}\text{-Cl}$ NCs were reported to exhibit negligible emission.⁸³ However, substituting chlorine with thiol ligands, while maintaining the metallic Au_{11} core, triggered room-temperature phosphorescence in $\text{Au}_{11}\text{-SH}$ NCs with μs -range lifetimes. A similar effect was observed by Crawford et al.,⁸⁴ who studied aqueous Au NCs with a size of ~ 1.7 nm. Initially, these phosphine-terminated Au NCs demonstrated no emission. However, μs -range NIR PL was induced upon ligand exchange with sulfur-containing ligands. Notably, this PL activation was consistently observed not only for thiolated ligands but also for other sulfur-containing ligands, including proteins. No PL response was detected when ligand exchange was performed with non-thiolated or thioester-containing ligands.

Interestingly, PL activation was also observed when thiol-containing ligands replaced initial ligands that were not only phosphine-based but also other non-thiolated ligands, such as folic acid or polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP). HRTEM and ^1H NMR experiments confirmed that the core size of the Au NCs remained essentially unchanged after ligand exchange, regardless of the ligand type. These findings strongly support the idea that metal-sulfur (M–S) interactions play a critical role in phosphorescence across various nanocrystalline systems.

It comes as no surprise that metal NCs from the same coinage metal group (Group 11 of the Periodic Table) exhibit similar PL properties. Indeed, many luminescent DNA- or polymer-protected silver NCs have been reported to show fluorescence in the nanosecond range.^{85,86} However, thiolated dihydrolipoic acid (DHLLA)-capped Ag NCs emitting near 660–680 nm have been demonstrated to exhibit μs -range PL lifetimes.^{87,88}

Similar to Au NCs, Cu NCs that are ligand-free or stabilized with weakly bound ligands have been shown to follow the simple spherical jellium model and emit in the UV/blue region with short ns-range lifetimes. Conversely, Cu NCs stabilized with strongly bound ligands, including thiolate ligands, and emitting in the orange and red spectral ranges exhibit significantly prolonged μs -range lifetimes.³⁸ The PL of all these NCs should not be considered individually, as they evidently share a common nature.

It is important to note that, although metal NCs protected with sulfur-containing ligands often exhibit phosphorescence, there are also reports of metal NCs stabilized with sulfur-free ligands emitting in the μs range. For instance, phosphine-protected Au_{13} NCs, either in solution or embedded in polymers, have been reported to emit in the NIR region (750–830 nm) with lifetimes of a few microseconds.^{83,89} Theoretical calculations for these Au_{13} NCs estimated radiative lifetimes in the range of several tens of microseconds.⁹⁰ A series of bimetallic

M@Au₁₂ (M=Pd, Pt, Rh, Ir) NCs protected with phosphine ligands (dppe or dppm) also revealed similar long-lived PL.^{91,92} Similarly, N-heterocyclic carbene (NHC)-stabilized Au NCs with red emission (PL peaks near 650–710 nm) demonstrated comparable lifetimes.^{93,94} Additionally, since the report by Rück et al. in 2021, some DNA-capped Ag NCs have been shown to emit long-lived NIR PL with lifetimes ranging from a few to several tens of μ s.^{95,96} These findings suggest that long-lived PL may not be exclusively attributed to metal-sulfur interactions. Other types of metal-ligand bonds, ligand-specific interactions, or oxygen-related interactions may also contribute to the prolonged PL lifetimes, offering an intriguing avenue for further exploration and study.

Distributions of decay constants

In the previous section, we demonstrated a similarity in the PL averaged lifetime dispersions between Au NCs and PbS QDs. Beyond averaged lifetimes, however, the shapes of decay curves can provide⁹⁷ significant insights into the relaxation dynamics of a sample. Time-resolved decay kinetics of both PbS QDs and Au NCs have been shown to exhibit non-exponential profiles.^{56,98} In previous studies, these decay kinetics were often analyzed using multi-exponential fitting models. For instance, the reported slow kinetics of Au NCs were fitted with two,^{50,52,74,99} three,^{44,100,101} or even four^{39,46} exponential components. In our recent studies on semiconductor QDs, we emphasized the importance of cautious interpretation of the physical meaning behind multi-exponential fitting models.^{56,97} A similar challenge applies to inhomogeneous ensembles of metallic NCs, which contain an almost infinite number of NCs and are likely to exhibit a near-continuous distribution of decay components rather than a discrete set of processes. In contrast, the decay profile of an individual nanoparticle is most likely mono-exponential.^{66,97}

Alternatively to the multi-exponential fitting model, the stretched exponential model has been employed to fit PL time traces of Au NCs.^{25,59,76} While this model can be effective in extracting averaged decay lifetimes, it is crucial to note that the underlying Lévy-stable distribution of rates assumed by this model is not physically realistic due to its diverging moments.⁹⁷

To verify the assumption of a continuous distribution of decay components and to retrieve this distribution, we applied an unbiased regularization approach based on the MEM/NLS method for fitting PL kinetics. Figure 3 presents the recovered normalized rate distributions for both Au NCs (dark cyan curves) and PbS QDs (purple curves) at selected emission wavelengths. The results clearly indicate that not only the PL spectra (Figure 1 and 2), but also the rate (lifetime) distributions are broader for Au NCs compared to PbS QDs. These recovered distributions of decay components are evidently continuous, suggesting that multi-exponential fitting models, if applied, lack physical significance in this context. Instead, such models can only serve as tools for estimating averaged lifetime values. It is important to highlight that MEM fitting generally allows for differentiation between continuous and discrete distributions of components, provided the discrete components are sufficiently well-separated.¹⁰²

Figure 3. Normalized rate distributions of Au NCs (dark cyan) and PbS QDs (purple) with a relative concentration of 25% for emission spectral intervals (a) or selected wavelengths (b). In panel (b), these selected emission wavelengths correspond to an energy of ~ 1.48 eV, following the spectral adjustments presented in Figure 2. The red dash-dotted and dashed lines represent log-normal fits of the distributions for Au NCs and PbS QDs, respectively.

Figure 2 demonstrated a remarkable overlap between the PL averaged lifetimes of Au NCs and spectrally adjusted, scaled PbS QDs. To further investigate, we analyzed the PL decay profiles corresponding to the emission energy near 1.48 eV, following the spectral adjustments presented in Figure 2, and compared the resulting rate distributions of the samples, as depicted in Figure 3b. The distribution shapes for both samples are fundamentally similar, resembling log-normal distributions with slightly extended tails. The retrieved distribution functions appear physically meaningful, as they properly converge to zero at extreme values of the argument (i.e., zero and infinity), regardless of whether the argument is expressed as lifetimes (not shown) or rates. This behavior is consistent with the log-normal distribution's characteristic of preserving its shape across rate and lifetime scales.⁹⁷

The broader distributions (Figure 3) observed for Au NCs compared to PbS QDs suggest greater inhomogeneity in the electronic states of Au NCs. This increased variability could be attributed to several factors, including their higher optical sensitivity to any irregularities in the nanoclusters or ligands, external distortions, molecular vibrations, and so on. Several factors contribute to this sensitivity, including a lower number of atoms, core-shell nanocluster-ligand structures, and others.

Conclusions

This study presents a detailed comparative investigation into the optical properties of semiconductor PbS QDs and metallic Au NCs, highlighting their similarities and differences in optical absorption, photoluminescence (PL), and emission kinetics. The absorption spectra reveal fundamental distinctions: PbS QDs exhibit sharp excitonic peaks characteristic of QC effects, while Au NCs display broad, featureless absorption attributed to molecular-like electronic states.

Despite these fundamental differences in absorption electronic states, both PbS QDs and Au NCs exhibit similar long-lived PL with μs -range lifetimes. Interestingly, while the PL spectra and rate distributions of Au NCs are significantly broader compared to those of PbS QDs, the dispersions of PL averaged lifetimes demonstrate a remarkable similarity. This suggests that their emission behaviors are at least partially governed by a shared photophysical mechanism, seemingly independent of the conventional QC model. We provided an extensive discussion emphasizing the critical role of metal- interactions in driving long-lived PL properties. In PbS QDs, these metal-sulfur bonds are inherent, whereas in Au NCs, sulfur atoms are introduced via sulfur-containing ligands.

The non-exponential nature of the decay kinetics observed in both Au NCs and PbS QDs was attributed to a continuous distribution of decay components across the ensemble, rather than to multiple discrete relaxation mechanisms. The shapes of these distributions were found to closely resemble log-normal functions.

This work bridges the gap between semiconductor and metal nanostructures, shedding light on the universal principles that govern nanoscale emission phenomena. These findings have the potential to broaden the understanding of nanoscale photophysics and inspire innovation in the design and application of nanomaterials for optoelectronics and bioimaging, fostering advancements across material science disciplines.

Experimental procedures

Sample fabrication and characterization:

Details on the sample preparation and characterization of PbS QDs can be found in our previous study.⁵⁶ Briefly, OA-capped core-type PbS QDs in toluene were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich, with a nominal mass concentration of 10 mg/ml in the stock solution.. Based on

absorption and emission peaks, the mean size of the PbS QDs was estimated to be 2.82 ± 0.08 nm. For this study, two samples were selected with concentrations of 6.25% and 25% relative to the original stock solution.

Comprehensive details of the synthesis process and characterization of Au NCs are provided in our previous works.^{98,103} In summary, an aqueous solution of Au NCs stabilized by thioctic acid and poly(ethylene glycol) with thiol end groups was synthesized. The carboxyl groups on thioctic acid were chemically bonded to benzylamine through EDC-activated amidation of surface carboxyl groups. High-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HRTEM) determined the average size of the Au NCs to be 1.4 ± 0.4 nm, consistent with a mean diameter of 1.2 ± 0.4 nm reported by Aldeek et al.,⁴⁴ where the same PL emission peak was observed. The composition and structural features of the clusters were confirmed through elemental analysis, inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectroscopy, and proton nuclear magnetic resonance (¹H NMR) spectroscopy, verifying the successful attachment of benzylamide groups to the Au NCs. The sample has also been carefully examined to exclude the presence of aggregates.

Optical spectroscopy methods:

The absorption spectra were recorded using a double-beam spectrophotometer (Specord 250, Analytik Jena). PL spectra were measured using a custom-built micro-spectroscopy setup based on an inverted optical microscope (Olympus IX-71). Wide-field excitation was used in the epifluorescence configuration using 405 nm (LDM405.120.CWA.L, Omicron) and 510 nm (MDL-III-510, CNI Optoelectronics) diode lasers for Au NCs and PbS QDs, respectively. The PbS QDs used in this study have been shown to exhibit⁵⁶ minimal dependence on the excitation wavelength, indicating that excitation at 405 nm should yield comparable results.

The emitted signal was divided by a short-pass dichroic beam-splitter and directed onto the input slits of two detection spectrographs. The visible spectral range ($\sim 350\text{--}950\text{ nm}$) was measured using a 30 cm imaging spectrograph equipped with a back-thinned LN-cooled CCD camera (Spec-10:400B, Princeton Instruments), while the NIR wavelengths ($\sim 950\text{--}1640\text{ nm}$) were detected using a 50 cm imaging spectrograph coupled with an InGaAs camera (NIRvana, Princeton Instruments). The spectral sensitivity of the entire apparatus was calibrated over a broad VIS-NIR spectral range using a 45 W tungsten-halogen lamp (secondary radiation standard, Newport Oriel).¹⁰⁴

PL decay kinetics were measured using the same micro-spectroscopy setup. The side exit ports of the spectrometers were equipped with photon-counting hybrid photomultipliers (Becker & Hickl HPM-100-50.C for visible light and Hamamatsu H10330A-45 for near-infrared), which detected the selected spectral regions. The signal was processed using a pair of multichannel scaler cards (Becker & Hickl MSA-300). Long rectangular excitation pulses were generated from continuous 405 nm (MDL-III-405, CNI Optoelectronics) or 510 nm (MLL-III-510, CNI Optoelectronics) laser beams using a silica acousto-optical modulator to measure PL time traces of Au and PbS samples, respectively. The repetition rate was set to 16.7 kHz or 30 kHz with a 25% duty cycle, resulting in pulse lengths of $\sim 15\ \mu\text{s}$ for PbS QDs and $\sim 8.3\ \mu\text{s}$ for Au NCs. Special care was taken to account for the effects of excitation pulse length and intensity on the accurate determination of decay times, as detailed in our recent publications.^{105,97}

Details on the extraction of average lifetimes and lifetime distributions:

Recently, we demonstrated that the non-exponential PL time traces of PbS QDs can be effectively modelled using a three-exponential decay model.⁵⁶ Similar to PbS QDs, we found that a three-exponential model was sufficient to provide a satisfactory fit for the PL kinetics of

Au NCs used in this study. However, in this work, we employed a fitting-free approach based on integration to compute the average recombination lifetimes of emitted photons. The intensity-averaged lifetime, $\bar{\tau}_{\text{int}}$, was calculated^{7,97} using the following formula:

$$\bar{\tau}_{\text{int}} = \frac{\int_0^{\infty} tI(t)dt}{\int_0^{\infty} I(t)dt} \quad (1)$$

where t represents the time elapsed since the start of the decay and $I(t)$ is the PL intensity as a function of time.

All calculations involving Equation 1 were performed using custom home-written Python code. Given that the decays were slow (in the μs range), we avoided deconvolution with the instrument response function (IRF) by truncating the initial 100 ns of the experimental decay curves (the IRF time interval corresponding to the switching time of the AO modulator). This approach mitigated minor distortions caused by the IRF.

By applying this truncation, there is a potential loss of any fast decay components (<100 ns). However, the absence of such components was verified by the lack of any significant drop in PL intensity at the beginning of decay immediately after the end of laser pulse.⁴⁹ This conclusion was further corroborated by comparing results from the truncated curves with fits of the original, unmodified decay curves, ensuring that the introduced error was negligible.

Unbiased lifetime distributions were obtained by fitting the experimental PL decay curves using a hybrid Maximum Entropy Method combined with Non-Linear Least Squares (MEM/NLS) analysis. This procedure was performed with the open-source MEMExp software,^{106,107} which offers robust capabilities for resolving complex lifetime distributions.

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Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

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